

EGATSIZ TEKIS SHUDGORLAYDIGAN PLUG

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Annotatsiya. An'anaviy pluglarning tuproqqa ishlov berish sifati agrotexnik talablarga javob bermaydi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi egatsiz tekis shudgorlaydigan plugni ishlab chiqish. Taklif qilingan plug vintsimon qo'shkorpus, birinchi qator surgirchlar, yo'naltirgichli orqa vintsimon o'ng va chap tomonga ag'daradigan korpuslar va ikkinchi qator tuproqsurgirchlardan iborat. Egatsiz tekis shudgorlaydigan plugning tajriba nusxasi yasalgan. Ishlab chiqilgan plugning dala sinovlari natijalari keltirilgan. O'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar natijasiga ko'ra egatsiz tekis shudgorlaydigan plug belgilangan texnologik ish jarayonini ishonchli bajaradi va uning ish ko'rsatkichlari agrotexnika talablarga to'liq mos keladi. Bunda mavjud pluglarga nisbatan sarflanadigan yonilg'i-moylash materiallari 21,26 % ga kamaygan.

Kalit so'zlar: texnologiya, an'anaviy shudgorlash, palaxsa, plug, ochiq egat, egatsiz tekis shudgorlash, korpus, qo'shkorpus.

Abstract. The quality of tillage with traditional plowing plows does not meet the agrotechnical requirements. The purpose of the research is to develop a plow for smooth, rowless plowing. A plow for smooth plowing is proposed, which contains twin screw housings, first-row colliders, rear screw right- and left-turning plow housings, second-row colliders. An experimental sample of a plow for smooth plowing was made. The results of field tests of the developed plow are presented. It is established that the quality indicators of the plow fully comply with agrotechnical requirements. At the same time, the degree of reduction in fuel consumption compared to the existing plow is 21,26 %.

Keywords: technology, traditional plowing, ripper, plow, ochik egat, smooth smooth plowing, housing, double housing.

Respublikamizda qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyotning muhim tarmog'idan biri hisoblanadi. Qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqarishida mehnat va energiya sarfini kamaytirish, resurslarni tejash, qishloq xo'jalik ekinlarini ilg'or texnologiyalar asosida yetishtirish va yuqori unumli qishloq xo'jalik mashinalarini ishlab chiqish yuzasidan keng qamrovli chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilib, jumladan dalalarni bir o'tishda ekishga tayyorlashda kam energiya sarflab, barcha texnologik jarayonlarni sifatli bajarilishini ta'minlaydigan texnika vositalarini ishlab chiqishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Quyida yopiq va yarim ochiq kesish sharoitida egatsiz tekis shudgorlaydigan plugning tuzilishi, asosiy parametrlari va uning sinov natijalari keltirilgan.

Yopiq va yarim ochiq kesish sharoitida egatsiz tekis shudgorlaydigan plugning tuzilishi va ish jarayoni

O'tkazilgan nazariy va eksperimental tadqiqotlar asosida yopiq va yarim ochiq kesish sharoitida egatsiz tekis shudgorlash texnologiyasi (1-rasm) va uni

amalga oshiradigan plug (shartli markasi PF-4) ishlab chiqilib, Qashqadaryo viloyatining Qarshi tumani fermer xo'jaliklarida dala va xo'jalik sinovlari o'tkazildi.

Plug disksimon pichoq 1, qo'sh vinsimon korpuslar 2, birinchi qator surgichlari 3, vinsimon o'ng va chapga ag'daruvchi korpuslar 4 va 5, ikkinchi qator surgichlar 7 dan iborat. Birinchi qator surgichlar 3 ning lezviyasi o'ng va chapga ag'daruvchi korpuslar 4 va 5 lardan oldin, ikkinchi qator surgichlar 7 esa ulardan keyin joylashgan. Vinsimon o'ng va chapga ag'daruvchi korpuslar 4 va 5 vinsimon yo'naltiruchi plastinalar 8 bilan jihozlangan Ular 4 va 5 korpuslarning lemexiga kalta lemexlar 6 yordamida berkitiladi. Korpus 4 va 5 ning dala qirrasidan yo'naltiruvchi plastina 8 gacha bo'lgan ko'ndalang masofa V_s korpuslar 4 va 5 ning qamrash kengligi V_k dan katta, yo'naltiruvchi plastina 8 ning, ya'ni uning qanotini qamrash kengligi b_z korpuslarning ishlov berish chuqurligiga a ga teng.

1-rasm. Yopiq va yarim ochiq kesish sharoitida egatsiz tekis shudgorlaydigan plug va ish texnologiyasi (1-rasm) va uni amalga oshiradigan plug

2-rasm. Yopiq va yarim ochiq kesish sharoitida egatsiz tekis shudgorlaydigan plugning old tomonidan ko'rinishi

3-rasm. ARION-630 traktoriga osilgan yopiq va yarim ochiq kesish sharoitida egatsiz tekis shudgorlaydigan plug

Plugning osma qurilmasi uni 4 va 5 klassdagi traktorlar bilan ishlatishga mo'ljallangan. Disksimon pichoq va tayanch g'ildiraklari seriyali ishlab chiqariladi. Plug tayanch g'ildiraklarini rostlash mexanizmi shudgor chuqurligini 22-30 sm chegarasida o'zgartirish imkonini beradi.

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